

DELAMINATION OPTIMIZATION OF HOOP WOUND COMPOSITE FLYWHEELS

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with improvements to an existing design for an energy storage flywheel (analogue momentum wheel) formerly built and tested by the authors company. To increase operational speed, the following well known problems have to be solved: the deformation compatibility between the inner disc (which delivers the inertia moment) and the outer filament wound case, the connection of the case with the driving shaft, and the delamination in the disc. In order to reduce the delamination problem the disc has to be built up of several subrings each having a higher density and a lower stiffness than its adjacent outer subring. In this paper an analytical design method (to determine the subring thickness value and required material for the disc) is presented. Further a brief design description for the dome and hoop ring geometry is given. A theoretical verification of the chosen design is performed with the finite element code NASTRAN using PATRAN for pre- and postprocessing.

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE DESIGN PROBLEM

1.1 General Introduction to Flywheels

Flywheels have been used for a long time to save energy in reciprocating machinery (/1/, /2/). The kinetic energy E and its specified useable portion in a flywheel (fig. 1.1) are defined by the equations

$$E = \theta_{p01} \Omega^2 / 2, \quad E_U = \theta_{p01} \cdot (\max \Omega^2 - \min \Omega^2) / 2, \quad (1)$$

whilst the specified power is given as $N = dE/dt = \theta_{p01} \cdot \Omega \cdot d\Omega/dt$, where θ_{p01} is the polar moment of inertia, t is time, $\max \Omega$ is the maximal angular speed - determined by the allowable stress - and $\min \Omega$ the specified rate for energy release or absorption. Since

$$r \cdot \Omega = v \quad \text{and} \quad (\sigma/\rho) \sim v \quad (2)$$

with r : = radius, v : = hoop speed, σ : = stress and ρ : = density, the specific energy capacity of such an energy storage flywheel is proportional to the so called specific strength of the material used:

$$E / \text{system mass} \sim (\sigma/\rho). \quad (3)$$

The development of high strength fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) extends the capacity reached so far. So flywheels should become capable of bringing sufficient energy for use in automotive and spacecraft applications. Advantages of the composite flywheels are: a) less risky at eventual burst (benign crash), and b) the bearing loads at burst of shape-similar and energy-similar flywheels are lower for the faster (composite) one.

A variety of flywheel types have been investigated using the mechanical information

that E grows linearly with θ_{p01} and quadratically with $\max \Omega$, where $\max \Omega$ might be influenced to some extent by the so-called fatigue stress ratio $R = \min \sigma / \max \sigma$ (representing the so called mean stress effect). So as not to get too large stress variations in energy storage wheels with respect to N, two R-determining design parameters θ_{p01} and Ω can be used linearly in the design process of the flywheel.

1.2 Design Requirements

- . Low mass of flywheel, including its safety chamber
- . Low production and operational costs of the whole system
- . Low safety risks (no metallic fittings in the outer parts)
- . Good out-of-balance quality. No spherical gyroscope ($\theta_{p01} = \theta_{aequ}$). Critical speeds $\omega = 2\pi f$, of rotor should not coincide with Ω and the nat. frequency of the chamber.
- . Enough stiffness of chamber and bearing casings to withstand the gyroscopic effects in curves and on an uneven roads. Small axial deformation.
- . Optimum: Stress level at each material point is at the allowable level. No creep.

1.3 Delamination Problem Formulation and Solution Hypothesis

When designing and testing a composite disc, delamination, caused by excessive radial stresses, sets a limit to the useable capacity (in the composite) of advanced fibres. This limit has to be shifted to as high a level as possible.

Solution Hypothesis:

- . Design a disc to bring the radial stress to approximately zero
- . Split the solid disc into subrings that deform compatibly.

2. ANALYTICAL SOLUTION FOR A RADIAL LOADED HOOP RING

2.1 Mechanical Model

Closed form solutions for a radial loaded ring respectively for a rotating orthotropic disc of constant thickness with a hole in the center, are found in the literature (e.g. /1/).

The analysis of these discs is based on the following assumptions:

- . Elasticity theory of anisotropic bodies is valid
- . Macroscopically homogeneous, transversally isotropic material
- . Principal (natural) axes of orthotropy coincide with the principal axes of the circular disc (\hat{z} coordinate system of the structure)
- . Plane stress state ($\sigma_3 = \sigma_{ax} = 0$)
- . Constant thickness and no self weight.

With these assumptions the equilibrium equation takes the form (see fig. 2.1)

$$\frac{d\sigma_r}{dr} + \frac{1}{r} (\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta) + \rho \cdot \Omega^2 \cdot r = 0 \quad (4)$$

and the strain-stress relations in polar coordinates can be written

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_r \\ \epsilon_\theta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_r & -\nu_{r\theta}/E_r \\ (\text{symm}) & 1/E_\theta \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_r \\ \sigma_\theta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

with E_r and E_θ the elasticity moduli in radial and hoop direction and $\nu_{r\theta}$ the major Poisson's ratio (in radial direction caused by hoop stresses σ_θ).

With respect to the rotational symmetry ($\gamma=0$) the strain-radial displacement relations are

$$\epsilon_r = du/dr, \quad \epsilon_\theta = u/r. \quad (6)$$

2.2 Solution of the Differential Equation

Putting $\sigma_r = 0$ the following equations remain (hole: $r \neq 0$)

$$\sigma_\theta = \rho \Omega^2 r^2, \quad du/dr = -\sigma_\theta \cdot \nu_{r\theta} / E_\theta, \quad u/r = \sigma_\theta / E_\theta. \quad (7)$$

Differentiating the last equation and introducing $\sigma_\theta = \rho \Omega^2 r$ delivers

$$du/dr = [3E_\theta \Omega^2 r^2 - \Omega^2 r^3 dE_\theta/dr] / E_\theta. \quad (8)$$

Equating the two equations for du/dr gives

$$-\rho \Omega^2 r^2 \nu_{r\theta} / E_\theta = [3E_\theta r^2 - r^3 dE_\theta/dr] \rho \Omega^2 / E_\theta$$

and a differential equation for the determination of E_θ

$$r dE_\theta/dr - (3 + \nu_{r\theta}) E_\theta = 0. \quad (9)$$

Case: $\nu = \text{constant}$

The general solution of equation (9) is $E_\theta(r) = C \cdot r^{(3 + \nu_{r\theta})}$. (10)

The constant C has to be determined by simulating a realistic, stepwise distribution of $E_\theta(r)$ of a disc built up by several rings.

Case: $\nu_{r\theta} = a + br/r_0$

Now the general solution is $E_\theta(r) = C \cdot e^{br/r_0} \cdot r^{(3+a)}$. (11)

2.3 Choice of Subrings and their Material

To apply the formula (9) the inner radius of the disk is set to two thirds of the outer one (table 2.1) $r_i = 2r_0/3$. (12)

Case: $\nu_{r\theta} = \text{constant}$

According to the knowledge that the solution is relatively insensitive to $\nu_{r\theta}$, the value 0.3 is taken.

Splitting the disc into 3 subrings of equal thickness, the curve points in table 2.1 are found, which lead to the material proposal down in that table.

Case: $\nu_{r\theta} = a + br/r_0$

The material choice leads to the numbers in the bottom part of table 2.1. They show the effect of varying Poisson's ratio in this application is insignificant.

3. DETERMINATION OF GEOMETRY AND MATERIAL DATA

A flywheel built at MAN a couple of years ago was redesigned to achieve approximately zero axial deformation at the hub fittings. This yielded a flat shape of the dome for centrifugal loading.

For the different parts of the flywheel the following materials were taken: CFRP (T800/epoxide) for the shell and the outer subring; CFRP (T300/epoxide) for the inner subring; GFRP (E-Glass/Epoxide) for the inner subring and aluminium for the hub fitting. The material data used for the computations are summarised in table 3.1.

4. FINITE ELEMENT METHOD VERIFICATION OF SYSTEM AND ITS' PARTS

MSC-NASTRAN was used for the FEM analysis. For preparing the FEM model and presentation of the results, the pre- and postprocessing program PATRAN was used. The calcu-

lation was linear elastic, and, for simplicity, the compression modulus was set equal to the tension modulus. The centrifugal loading was a unity loading according to 100 m/s speed at the outer diameter of 520 mm.

The flywheel FEM model with the various materials indicated, is shown in fig. 4.1. The centrifugal loading required only an axial symmetric idealization with DOF's 246 constrained at each node. A two degree sector of one symmetrical half of the model was meshed with the third DOF constrained additionally at the cross section. The different materials as well as shell and solid elements were connected by rigid bars. The model comprises 656 node points: 183 solid elements, 64 shell elements and 142 rigid bars. The hub fittings were not fixed to the shaft. In the outer area gliding was allowed between the hoop wound ring and the outer shell.

Fig. 4.2 shows the radial stress profile in the hubring and fig. 4.3 the hoop (global) stress σ_{θ} in the whole system.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- . The main result of this investigation was that the negative radial stresses in fig. 4.2, calculated for the hoop ring, confirm that the subring-design chosen solves the delamination problem. This makes the operational speed not longer dependent on the delamination limit
- . The matrix stresses in the dome (T800) will exceed the fatigue strength at about 600 m/s. But the cracks arising will not necessarily limit the operational speed so long as they do not cause too large out of balance forces
- . The fibre strength would allow a much higher speed, at approximately 800 m/s, which however would require a redesign of the highly stressed aluminium hub fitting.

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6. REFERENCES

- /1/ TANG, Sam: Elastic stresses in Rotating Anisotropic Disks. Int. J. Mech. Si., Pergamon Press, 1969, p. 509-517.
- /2/ Lockheed Missiles and Space Company: Flywheel Feasibility Study and Demonstration. LMSC-D 007915 (Final Report), Sunnyvilly, CA, 1971.
- /3/ Volume 2: Energy Storage Devices; 2. Mechanical Devices.
- /4/ Schwungradentwicklung der MAN-NT für Arge Gyrobus. BMFT-Förderungskurzzeichen TV 7650 B7 (1976-1980)
- /5/ CUNTZE, Ralf, Georg: Grundlagen für die Berechnung von Rotationsschalen aus Faserkunststoffverbund. Habilitationsschrift, Techn. Univ. München, 1978.

Fig. 1.1 Proposed Geometry for an Improved Flywheel

Fig. 2.1
Equilibrium Stress State
in a Ring Element

$(\frac{r}{r_0})$	$\frac{13}{18}$	$\frac{15}{18}$	$\frac{17}{18}$	
$(\frac{r}{r_0})^{3+\nu r\theta} \sim E_\theta$	0.34 ≅ 41%	0.54 ≅ 66%	0.83 ≅ 100%	$\nu_{\perp\parallel} = 0.3$
Proposal for Fibres:	E-Glas	T300	T800	
	GFRP	CFRP		
$E_\theta \hat{=} E_{\parallel}$ (achieved)	27%	70%	100%	
$\nu r\theta \hat{=} \nu_{\perp\parallel}$	0.32	0.30	0.22	

Table 2.1
Requirements for Distribution
of E_θ and
Material Proposal for the
Hoop Ring.
Matrix: epoxide.
Fibre volume fraction: 60%
 $r_0 = 258$ mm
(The 27% for GFRP instead of
42% improve the situation)

E_θ requirement for mat. proposal	$E_\theta(r)$			$\nu_{\perp\parallel} \approx a + \frac{b \cdot r}{r_0}$
$(\frac{r}{r_0})^{3+a} e^{br/r_0}$	42%	67%	100%	$= 0.66 - 0.45 r/r_0$

		GFK E-Glas	CFK T300	CFK T800	Alum.
$E_{\parallel t}$	N/mm ²	50000	130000	185000	71000
$E_{\perp t}$	N/mm ²	9000	8500	6500	-
$G_{\#}$	N/mm ²	5000	5500	5000	-
$\nu_{\perp\parallel}$	-	0.32	0.30	0.22	0.30
$\nu_{\parallel\perp}$	-	0.38	0.40	0.40	-
$R_{\parallel t}$	N/mm ²	600	1200	1700	-
$R_{\parallel c}$	N/mm ²	500	1000	1300	-
$R_{\perp t}$	N/mm ²	30	40	35	-
$R_{\perp c}$	N/mm ²	100	140	135	-
$\tau_{\#}$	N/mm ²	50	65	60	-
ρ	g/cm ³	2.01	1.59	1.56	2.80

Table 3.1
Material Input Data.
Values for fatigue.
(Fibre volume fraction
60%, $R = \min\sigma/\max\sigma = 0$,
 $E_{\parallel c} = E_{\parallel t}$, $E_{\perp c} = E_{\perp t}$
(safe side),
 $G_{\parallel\perp} = E_{\perp}/(2(1+\nu_{\perp\parallel}))$,
damage dependant values)

Fig. 4.1 FEM-Model with Material and Boundary Conditions

Fig. 4.3 Hoop Stress σ_θ of the Entire Flywheel

FOR SHELL ELEMENTS AT OUTER LAYER
FOR SOLID ELEMENTS AT CENTROID

UY=.0247 UZ=0

Fig. 4.2 Radial Stress σ_r of the Hoop Ring

